

AN AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF SENSORINEURAL HEARING LOSS (*BADHIRYA*) – A CASE STUDY

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Article Received on
01 August 2025,

Revised on 21 August 2025,
Accepted on 11 Sept. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17213566>

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ABSTRACT

The inner ear is the main culprit of sensorineural hearing (SNHL), which is a specific type of hearing loss. Peripheral and Central SNHL (auditory pathway or cortex) can be distinguished. It might be congenital or acquired. Congenital: resulting from prenatal or perinatal conditions or from defects of the inner ear. About 90% of reported cases of hearing loss are related to it. There is currently no suggested course of treatment for it. Hearing loss is associated with *Badhirya* (hearing loss) in *Ayurveda*, and our *Acharyas* have prescribed numerous therapeutic techniques and formulations for the effective treatment in improving the hearing capacity of a 47-year-old-male patient who has moderate to severe SNHL since 1 years. He was made

to undergo both *Ayurvedic* procedures and medications. The names of the *Ayurvedic* procedures adopted are *Nasya* (nasal drop) with *Anu taila*, *Karnapooran* with *Bilwa Taila* for 14 days, *Rasayana churna* and *Dashmoola kwath* internally for 45 days. The interventions resulted in a good improvement in hearing.

KEYWORDS: *Badhirya*, *Nasya*, *Karnapooran*, Sensorineural Hearing Loss.

INTRODUCTION

A person's capacity to hear is crucial to the development of their speech and language abilities. After an inner ear injury, sensory neural hearing loss, or SNHL, develop. SNHL may also go from your inner ear to your brain. Mild sounds could be difficult to grasp. Even louder sounds could sounds muffled or indistinct, the most prevalent kind of irreversible hearing loss is this one. Surgery or medication alone cannot usually correct SNHL. You could

hear better hearing aids.^[1] SNHL can vary in severity, from partial to total hearing loss, based on the extent of the injury.

1. Mild hearing loss: A loss of hearing between 26 to 40 decibels.
2. Moderate hearing loss: A loss of hearing between 41 to 55 decibels.
3. Severe hearing loss: hearing loss greater than 71 Db. Although SNHL is rarely life-threatening, improper management may cause communications difficulties, severe pathophysiological causes, including trauma, noise trauma, ototoxicity diabetes, autoimmune disease, congenital abnormalities, and consumptions of aminoglycoside medicine, contribute to inner ear damage and cause sudden hearing loss (SNHL). Its symptoms include tinnitus, ear fullness, and sudden or persistent hearing loss.

About 430 million people, or more than 5% of the global population – 432 million adults and 34 million children need rehabilitation to treat their hearing loss. It is projected that one in ten individuals, or more than 700million, will suffer from disabled hearing loss by the year 2050.^[2] A comfortable, financially feasible, and efficacious *Ayurvedic* treatment regimen. This illness can be compared to *Badhirya*, which is brought on by the *Sangatva* of *Shabdhavaha Srotas* (obstruction of the channel that carries sound waves) caused by Kapha and Vata Doshas, which is made worse by the person's unhealthy habits and way of life. In the first stages, revitalizing *Rasayana* therapies are used to cure it, along with *Vatahara Chikitsa*. Therefore, in an attempt to improve the illness state, we have implemented an *Ayurvedic* diet and treatment plan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The patient's hearing was normal before one years ago, but gradually he began to experience reduced hearing in both ears. He consulted an ENT physician and was advised to use a hearing aid, but he was not willing to do so. As a result, he decided to visit the *Shalaky Tantra* OPD ITRA, Jamnagar.

History of Past illness – Not a known case of DM/HTN

Family History – no any

Personal History

Appetite – Good

Sleep – Sound

Bowel – unsatisfactory

Micturition – 6-7 times/day

Diet – Mixed

EXAMINATION

Ear Examination

Otoscopy : EAC Right - clear

Left – clear

TM Right – Visible and Intact

Left -- Visible and Intact

Rinne's Test : Positive AC>BC B/L Ear

Weber's Test : Not lateralized

PTA : Right – Moderate sensorineural hearing loss

Left – Mild sensorineural hearing loss

Asthavidha Pareeksha

1. *nadi* – 76/min
2. *mala* – Prakruta
3. *Mutra* – Prakruta
4. *Jihva* – Prakruta/nirama
5. *Shabda* – Prakruta
6. *Drik* – Prakruta
7. *Akriti* – Madhyama
8. *Sparsh* – Prakruta

Dashvidha Pareeksha

1. *Prakruti* – VataPitta
2. *Vikriti* – no any
3. *Sara* – Madhyama
4. *Samhana* – Madhyama
5. *Satmya* – Madhyama
6. *Satva* – Madhyama
7. *Ahara Shakti* – Madhyama
8. *Vyayama Shakti* – Madhyama
9. *Vaya* – Madhyama
10. *Pramana* – Madhyama

General Examination

Respiratory system – Normal breathing sound heard, No added sounds

CVS – S1 S2 heard no added sounds

BP : 128/86 mm/hg

Pulse rate : 78/min

Treatment given

SN	Treatment	Medicine	Mode of administration	Duration
1.	Internally	<i>Shivakshara pachan churna</i>	3 gm BD with L.W.W.	7 days
		<i>Rasayana churna</i>	3gm BD after meal with <i>ghrita</i>	30days
2.	<i>Nasya</i>	<i>Anu Taila</i>	6 drops in each nostril at morning	7 days
3.	<i>Karnapooran</i>	<i>Bilwadi Taila</i>	QS- to both the ears	21 days

DISCUSSION

Sensorineural hearing loss, also known as *Badhirya*, is a prevalent ENT problem that presents significant challenge to ENT surgeons. Although the disease appears simple, patients often experience inadequate relief, even after multiple visits to the clinic. Consequently, the current medical system's approach to treating *Badhirya* (hearing loss) has not proven to be effective. In these situations, surgical intervention (cochlea implant) is uncommon and is only carried out when presented with complications. It is possible to use the "*Vata Vyadhi Chikitsa*" *Siddhanta* to manage *Badhirya*.^[3] In addition to these, Ayurveda provides a variety of treatment modalities for managing *Badhirya*, such as *Ghritapana* (consuming medicated ghee), *Rasayanasevana* (rejuvenating drugs), *Nasya* (nasal drops) *Snehana* (oleation therapy), *Swedana* (perspiration therapy), *Snehavirechana* (purgative therapy), *Sirobasti*, *Karnapoorna* (filling the ear with medicated oil), *Jalaukavacharana* (leech therapy), etc.^[4] However, the most commonly recommended procedures for managing *Badhirya* are *Karnapoorna* and *Nasya*. The function of *Indriyas* is enhanced by *Anu Taila Nasya (Karnaindriya)*. *Anu Taila* was planned, which calms the agitated *Doshas* in the head, aids in restoring the normal functioning of the central nervous system, and balances the blood flow to all of the sense organs, including the ears. Since *Shringataka Marma* in *Shira* is the point where all sense organs, including the eye, ear, and nose join together, any medication administered to this region helps to nourish the nerves that connect these places and targets the vitiated *Doshas* associated with each sense organ. One of the fundamental therapies for all *Karnarogas* listed

in Ayurvedic literature is *Karnpurana*.^[5] *Karnpurana*, with *Bilwadi Taila*, has the *Vatashamaka* property.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic medications alongside lifestyle modifications such as adhering to *Pathya* and avoiding *Apathya* as well as yoga practice, have improved the deceased's sensorineural hearing loss. As a result, it is both feasible and effective, and in the future, there should be more research done on this topic.

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